

Using knowledge graphs to infer gene expression in plants

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Abstract

Climate change is already affecting ecosystems around the world and forcing us to adapt to meet societal needs. The speed with which climate change is progressing necessitates a massive scaling up of the number of species with understood genotype-environment-phenotype (G×E×P) dynamics. An important part of predicting phenotype is understanding the complex gene regulatory networks present in organisms. Previous work has demonstrated that knowledge about one species can be applied to another using ontologically-supported knowledge bases that exploit homologous structures and homologous genes. These types of structures that can apply knowledge about one species to another have the potential to enable the massive scaling up that is needed through *in silico* experimentation. We developed one such structure, a knowledge graph (KG) using information from Planteome and the EMBL-EBI Expression Atlas that connects gene expression, molecular interactions, functions, pathways, and projections to homology-based gene annotations. Our preliminary analysis uses data from gene expression studies in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Populus trichocarpa* plants exposed to drought conditions. A graph query identified 16 pairs of homologous genes in these two taxa, some of which show opposite patterns of gene expression in response to drought. As expected, analysis of the upstream cis-regulatory region of these genes revealed that homologs with similar expression behavior had conserved cis-regulatory regions and potential interaction with similar trans-elements, unlike homologs that changed their expression in opposite ways. This suggests that even though the homologous pairs share common ancestry and functional roles, predicting expression and phenotype through homology inference needs careful consideration of integrating cis and trans regulatory components in the curated and inferred knowledge graph.

Introduction

Climate change is already affecting ecosystems around the world and forcing us to explore ways to adapt to meet societal needs. This is particularly true in crop science where researchers are working to identify and predict genes and their resulting phenotypes under different environmental conditions in order to secure food production under a new climate regime (Tian et

al. 2021; Thudi et al. 2021). Understanding gene/phenotype/environment relationships requires a large data set which can be difficult to collect, so most researchers focus on a small number of heavily studied species. The speed with which climate change is progressing necessitates a massive scaling up of the number of species with understood G/P/E dynamics. The research and the knowledge gained in this area will also help human exploration in space, where plants will play an important role ([Barker et al. 2023](#)). Previous work has demonstrated that knowledge about one species can be applied to another using ontologically-supported knowledgebases that exploit homologous structures and orthologous genes (e.g., (Naithani et al. 2020)). These types of knowledge structures that can apply knowledge about one species to another have the potential to enable the massive scaling up that is needed.

An important part of predicting phenotype is understanding the complex gene regulatory networks present in plants. This paper will focus on the promoter region, the 5' cis-regulatory regions of the homologs. This region is a portion of the DNA strand that is "upstream" from the 5' end of the gene's coding start site of the gene and provides selective binding sites for trans-acting factors like transcription factors, repressors, and activators that regulate the expression of the gene (Liu, White, and MacRae 1999). These regions are just one element of the gene expression process. Studying the expression of trans-acting factors is important for understanding the spatio-temporal dynamics of molecular interactions that help adapt or overcome stress. Resources like the Gene Ontology (The GO Consortium 2021), Planteome (Cooper et al. 2018), Plant Reactome (Naithani et al. 2020), and KnetMiner (Hassani-Pak et al. 2021) contain much of what we know about gene function, gene regulatory networks, and phenotypes in the form of Gene X regulates Gene Y and Gene Y impacts phenotype Z, but the contextual effect of environmental conditions under which these interactions happen are almost always not included in the annotations, since not all plants and their genes are characterized in detail and if it is included, the environment context is detailed only in the metadata.

Investigations that use protein domain identification and gene homology-based methods to infer the functional role a gene carries out in a given species, may be overlooking the spatial and temporal dynamics of mRNA expression that determines whether a gene product (protein) will be present at the desired time and place to serve a molecular function. The interactive nature of genes, environments, and phenotypes requires a data structure that can represent qualitative relationships (e.g., "has phenotype" or "regulates") and integrate heterogeneous data types in a single, queryable framework. One of these data structures is a knowledge graph (KG) (Sheth, Padhee, and Gyrard 2019).

A graph is made up of objects (nodes) and the relationships (edges) between those objects and, in this context, represents what we know about how biological and environmental entities (objects) interact. Rather than store data in a table or database, a knowledge graph stores the synthesized knowledge we gain from the data, e.g., Gene X has phenotype Y. As more knowledge is added to the graph, more complex queries, network analyses, and inferences can be drawn. An important example is the use of a biomedical knowledge graph linking diseases and phenotypes that was successfully used in rare disease diagnosis (Zemojtel et al. 2014). KGs used for translational science rarely contain environmental exposures even though we know environmental conditions are an important part of gene expression dynamics. The exact way to model exposures in a KG is still under development (Chan et al. 2023). A KG containing

information about plant genomics and phenomics under differing environmental conditions can be used to generate hypotheses *in silico* for targeting, thereby reducing the number of *in vivo* experiments that need to be done, saving time and resources.

This study examines gene expression patterns in response to drought conditions in four plant species: *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Zea mays*, *Sorghum bicolor*, and *Populus trichocarpa*. The central motivation of this work is to assess the feasibility of using homologs to make predictions about gene expression in multiple species.

Materials and Methods

Data Description

Planteome

The Planteome (<https://planteome.org/>) is a centralized web portal with a suite of interrelated ontologies for plants and a database of plant genomics data, annotated to the ontology terms (Cooper et al., 2018). In the October 2020 release (Version 4.0), the Planteome database included approximately 60,000 ontology terms, and more than 3 million data objects, which are connected to ontology terms through about 20 million associations. The Planteome database has plant genomic information covering 125 plant taxa. The data available in the Planteome, and annotated with ontology terms, includes plant gene expression data, traits, phenotypes, genomes and germplasm sources.

The ontologies developed in-house by the Planteome project include the Plant Ontology (PO; Cooper et al., 2013; Walls et al., 2019), which describes plant anatomical structures and developmental stages, the Plant Trait Ontology (TO) for traits and phenotypes, and the Plant Experimental Conditions Ontology (PECO), which describes experimental conditions and plant exposures. In addition to these, the Planteome hosts the collaborator reference ontologies- the Gene Ontology (GO; The Gene Ontology Consortium, 2021), Phenotype and Trait Ontology (PATO; Gkoutos et al., 2018) and also a number of species-specific trait dictionaries developed by the Crop Ontology (Shrestha et al., 2010; Arnaud et al., 2020). In the current release, the Planetome includes 11 of the CO trait dictionaries, mapped to the TO.

GO annotations were computationally generated for new species using InParanoid and InterProScan(Shulaev et al. 2011; Myburg et al. 2014). InParanoid was used to predict gene orthology based on the *Arabidopsis thaliana* associations generated by TAIR (Reiser et al. 2022). InterProScan was used to add GO annotations to genes via inference by analyzing protein families and domain mappings (Paysan-Lafosse et al. 2023).

EMBL-EBI Expression Atlas

The EMBL-EBI Expression Atlas (GXA) can be accessed online and is part of the European Bioinformatics Institute (Papatheodorou et al. 2020). It contains manually curated and analyzed

data from over 900 plant experiments that have been re-analyzed using the latest versions of the reference plant genome assembly and annotations and by deploying a standardized analysis workflow. Every experiment is fully documented with metadata and provenance.

Gene expression data were downloaded as a table from GXA after searching for desired species and environmental conditions. Data were filtered to include only genes that had statistically different gene expression ($p < 0.05$) compared to a baseline that was < -1 or > 1 . Genes with positive differential expression were annotated as having increased expression. Genes with negative differential expression were annotated as having decreased expression. The tabulated data were annotated with additional ontology terms where appropriate and made available in GitHub for graph construction.

Creating the Graph

The graph was created by combining data from Planteome, the GXA, the PO, the TO, the GO, and the PECO using the tools available at KG-Hub (Harry Caufield et al. 2023). First, the data and mapping files were downloaded from their respective data repositories. GO-Basic and NCBI Tax-Slim were downloaded from the OBO Foundry in javascript object notation (JSON) format. PO and TO were downloaded from the OBO Foundry in owl format and transformed to JSON using ROBOT (Jackson et al. 2019). Data files containing information about *Sorghum bicolor*, *Zea mays*, *Oryza sativa*, *Populus trichocarpa*, and *Arabidopsis thaliana* were downloaded from Planteome servers in GAF format. Data files containing differential gene expression data involving *Sorghum bicolor*, *Zea mays*, *Oryza sativa*, *Populus trichocarpa*, and *Arabidopsis thaliana* in drought and saline environments were downloaded from the GXA. Several mapping files were used to normalize gene and trait identifiers. Rice gene identifiers were mapped to *Oryza sativa* v7.0 using the ID converter file from the Rice Annotation Project Database (Sakai et al. 2013; Ouyang et al. 2007). Maize gene identifiers were mapped to Zm-B73-REFERENCE-NAM-5.0 assembly using a mapping file that includes all B73 assembly versions and includes the DAGchainer analysis which was obtained from MaizeGDB (Portwood et al. 2019; EMBL-EBI n.d.). Poplar gene identifiers were mapped to the reference genome using a mapping file from Gramene (Tello-Ruiz et al. 2018). *Sorghum* gene names were normalized to *Sorghum bicolor* v3.1.1 (McCormick et al. 2018). Plant traits and phenotypes were annotated with TO terms using a look-up dictionary file. Second, each of the data files was transformed to standardized nodes and edges in a tsv file using custom scripts. These scripts normalized gene and trait identifiers using ontologies and the provided mapping files and annotated every entity with a Biolink semantic type (Table 1) and relationships between entities were described using Biolink predicates (Table 2). The graph was assembled according to the Biolink model, which provides standard semantic types and relationships for biological entities (Unni et al. 2022).

There was not enough expression data to include *O. sativa* or saline environments in this analysis, but they were included in the graph.

Table 1: Identifiers and Biolink Semantic Types Assigned to Elements of the Graph

Biological Element	Identifier	Biolink Type
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Plant part	PO	Anatomical Entity
Growth stage	PO	Life stage
Plant trait	TO	Phenotypic Feature
<i>Zea mays</i> gene	Zm00001eb IDs	Genomic Entity
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> gene	Sobic IDs	Genomic Entity
<i>Oryza sativa</i> gene	LOC_Os IDs	Genomic Entity
<i>Populus trichocarpa</i> gene	POPTR IDs	Genomic Entity
Experimental condition	PECO	Environmental Exposure
QTL	Gramene IDs	Genomic Entity
Cultivar	NCBITaxonomy	Organismal Entity
Taxon	NCBITaxonomy	Organism Taxon
Cellular component	GO	Cellular Component
Molecular function	GO	Molecular Function
Biological process	GO	Biological Process
Germplasm	GRIN & IRIC IDs	Organismal Entity

The final step merged the transformed tsv files into a deduplicated list of nodes and edges in KGX format. The final graph consisted of over 400,000 nodes and over 5,000,000 edges and contains additional data from EOLTraitbank that was not used in this study (Fig 1). Specific information about categorical and numerical plant phenotypes was represented as an edge property (Fig 2).

Figure 1: Structure of the Knowledge Graph. Data are transformed using ontologies and the Biolink model to form a graph. Nodes (gray boxes) are labeled with Biolink semantic type and edges (gray arrows) are labeled with Biolink predicate. Arrows indicate directionality.

	Numerical Phenotypes	Categorical Phenotypes
has_attribute	Plant height	Decreased plant height
has_attribute_type	TO:0000207	TO:2000229
has_quantitative_value	12	
has_unit	cm	

Figure 2: Phenotype Data in Edge Properties. Detailed phenotype information is represented as a collection of edge properties that can accommodate numerical phenotypes and categorical phenotypes.

Table 2: Edges and Their Biolink Predicates

Subject Entity	Predicate Type	Object Entity
Genomic Entity	In taxon	Organism Taxon
Genomic Entity	Active in	Cellular Component

Genomic Entity	Regulates	Biological Process
Genomic Entity	Enables	Molecular Function
Genomic Entity	Expressed in	Anatomical Entity
Genomic Entity	Expressed in	Life Stage
Genomic Entity	Has phenotype	Phenotypic Feature
Genomic Entity	Orthologous to	Genomic Entity
Organism Taxon	Has phenotype	Phenotypic Feature
Organismal Entity	In taxon	Organism Taxon
Organismal Entity	Has phenotype	Phenotypic feature
Environmental Exposure	Increases expression of	Genomic Entity
Environmental Exposure	Decreases expression of	Genomic Entity

Querying the Graph

The merged node file and edge file were uploaded into neo4j for exploration and query. A Cypher query (Box 1) was used to find all of the homologous genes that had also been documented to have differential gene expression in either a drought or a saline environment, separately (Supplemental Data 1&2). The saline environment did not return enough data.

Box 1: Cypher Query

```
MATCH (e
{id:'PECO:0007404'})-[r]->(g), (g)-[q:`biolink:orthologous_to`]-
(h), (e {id:'PECO:0007404'})-[s]->(h) RETURN *
```

Genes returned from the query for the drought environment were compared based on GO annotations (Supplemental Data 3), but this also did not give enough data to make conclusions using PANTHER (Supplementary Data 4).

Comparing Promoter Regions

We collected 5'-regulatory regions of the identified genes (700-900 bp) using BioMart in the Gramene database (Spooner et al. 2012) and searched for potential transcription factor binding sites using PlantPAN (Chow et al. 2016). Using these data (Supplementary Data 5), we created a matrix comparing the occurrence of each transcription factor in the binding site of each gene pair and made note of which were or were not held in common. We used ClustVis (Metsalu and Vilo 2015) to examine the similarity between the transcription factor binding sites for each of the

Poplar and *Arabidopsis* gene pairs. Twelve transcription factor binding sites (AT-Hook, bHLH, C2H2, Dehydrin, Dof, GATA, Homeodomain, Myb/SANT, NF-YB, TBP, Trihelix, ZF-HD) were present in the promoter regions of all the genes studied and thus were removed from clustering analysis.

Data Availability

The merged KG data are hosted on the CyVerse DataCommons (<https://datacommons.cyverse.org/browse/iplant/home/shared/genophenoenvo>). The KG data are available for direct download or for remote visualization via CyVerse WebDav service (https://data.cyverse.org/dav-anon/iplant/commons/community_released/genophenoenvo/kg/) using visualization software such as Neo4J. The python code used to create the graphs are publicly hosted on GitHub (<https://github.com/genophenoenvo/knowledge-graph>). The final merged KG includes two tab separated value (tsv) files which include the edges and nodes.

Results

The graph query returned 62 pairs of homologous genes from *Sorghum bicolor*, *Zea mays*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*, and *Populus trichocarpa*, (Supplementary Data 6) but only 16 pairs between *A. thaliana* and *P. trichocarpa* had documented similar (8) and differential (8) expression in drought conditions (Table 3). All of the genes with similarly expressed pairs had decreased expression. Expression data for the 16 homologous pairs of *A. thaliana* and *P. trichocarpa* came from two studies in GXA (de Simone et al. 2017; Filichkin et al. 2018).

Table 3: Gene expression in *A. thaliana* and *P. trichocarpa* homologous genes under drought conditions

<i>A. thaliana</i> Gene*	<i>P. trichocarpa</i> Gene*	Gene Function (from Planteome)
AT3G49960 ↓	POPTR_007G053400v3 ↑	Peroxidase activity, response to oxidative stress, heme binding
AT1G70710 ↓	POPTR_010G109200v3 ↓	Catalytic activity, hyrolase activity, carbohydrate metabolic process
AT1G10550 ↓	POPTR_014G115000v3 ↓	Xyloglucan metabolism, hyrolase activity, carbohydrate metabolic process, cell wall biogenesis
AT5G67400 ↓	POPTR_007G053400v3 ↑	Peroxidase activity, response to oxidative stress, heme binding, hydrogen peroxide catabolic process
AT5G23210 ↓	POPTR_005G091700v3 ↓	Proteolysis, serine-type carboxypeptidase activity
AT1G67750 ↓	POPTR_008G182200v3 ↓	Pectate lyase activity, metal ion binding

AT2G39530 ↓	POPTR_010G205300v3 ↑	iron/sulfur cluster binding
AT5G13140 ↓	POPTR_003G167100v3 ↓	Response to nematode, pectate lyase activity, metal ion binding
AT1G11580 ↓	POPTR_011G025400v3 ↑	Enzyme inhibitor activity, pectinesterase activity, cell wall modification, rRNA N-glycosylase activity, aspartyl esterase activity, toxin activity, defense response
AT3G27400 ↓	POPTR_001G339500v3 ↑	Response to nematode, pectate lyase activity, metal ion binding
AT4G02330 ↓	POPTR_014G127000v3 ↑	Enzyme inhibitor activity, pectinesterase activity, cell wall modification, response to stress, aspartyl esterase activity
AT5G20630 ↓	POPTR_006G142600v3 ↓	Manganese ion binding, nutrient reservoir activity
AT4G26260 ↑	POPTR_018G069700v3 ↓	Iron ion binding, inositol oxygenase activity, syncytium formation, L-ascorbic acid biosynthetic pathway
AT2G44990 ↑	POPTR_014G056800v3 ↓	Oxidoreductase activity, secondary shoot formation, carotene catabolic process, strigolactone biosynthetic process, xanthophyll catabolic process, metal ion binding
AT1G70710 ↓	POPTR_010G109200v3 ↓	Cellulase activity, cell wall modification, hydrolase activity
AT1G12940 ↑	POPTR_015G081500v3 ↓	Transmembrane transport

*↓ Indicates decreased expression and ↑ indicates increased expression

Based on the predicted transcription factor binding sites in the promoter regions, the *Populus* genes in the differentially expressed homolog pairs cluster separately from the other *Populus* and *Arabidopsis* genes (Fig 1). This difference is driven by a group of 11 transcription factor binding sites that are absent in the promoter regions of the subset of divergent *Populus* genes (Fig. 2). The separation of these genes cannot be explained by taxon or study providing the data (which overlaps taxon).

Figure 1. Clustering of *Populus* and *Arabidopsis* genes based on similarity of the transcription factor binding sites in the promoter region - PCA. The *Populus* genes from the differentially expressed homolog pairs (blue circles) clustered away from the other *Populus* (blue) and *Arabidopsis* (red) genes. Differentially expressed genes are represented as circles and similarly expressed genes are represented as squares. Note that taxonomic differences (blue and red ovals) do not explain the differences in gene expression. No scaling is applied to rows; SVD with imputation is used to calculate principal components. X and Y axis show principal component 1 and principal component 2 that explain 25.1% and 9.5% of the total variance, respectively. N = 29 data points

There were seven *Populus* genes that clustered away from the others. All but one (POPTR_014G056800v3 involved in strigolactone biosynthesis) were hypothetical proteins (According to Gramene). GO annotations for these genes clustered around transporter activity, catabolic activity, response to stress, binding, and catalytic activity. The eleven transcription factors absent in the binding sites of the *Populus* genes include proteins involved in plant stress response in *Arabidopsis* (According to UniProt; Table 4).

Figure 2. Clustering of *Populus* and *Arabidopsis* genes based on similarity of the transcription factor binding sites in the promoter region - HeatMap. The clustering of these genes is driven by the absence of 11 transcription factor binding sites in the promoter region of a subset of *Populus* genes. Rows are centered; no scaling is applied to rows. Both rows and columns are clustered using correlation distance and average linkage. 58 rows, 29 columns.

Table 4. Transcription Factor Binding Sites Absent from the Differentially Expressed *Populus* Genes in This Study.

Transcription Factor
RAV
MIKC
NAM

G2-like
CPP
ARR-B
tify
TALE
NF-YC
ERF
NF-YA

Discussion

This work shows that one can use *in silico* experiments to predict gene expression in drought conditions using homologous gene families in some species pairs, but not all. This work supports previous findings that in some cases promoter regions evolve separately from the coding region of the genes they regulate (e.g., (Tirosh et al. 2008)). Thus, we can translate knowledge about gene expression in one species to another, but we need to include these dynamics in the data infrastructures we use to make this translation, in this case, KGs. Many data structures link a gene to a phenotype, trait, or disease without specific expression information. Current representation of differential gene expression links exposure to a chemical or a drug to the increased or decreased expression of a specific gene in the context of toxicology and drug development (Unni et al., n.d.; Fecho et al. 2022). Gene regulatory networks are represented as mini-networks of genes that influence other genes (The GO Consortium 2021), but many of these networks are still unknown in plants. In the short-term, *in silico* KG experiments involving gene expression can be given some validity by including empirically validated gene expression patterns of homologs

These opposing gene expression patterns are not a concern for researchers who are only interested in finding a list of genes that are potentially important in a specific context. It is not until one needs to generate hypotheses about the impact of the environment on biological function that more complex graph representations become needed. If we are to incorporate the effect of the environment, we need to know more than that Gene X has phenotype Y. We need to know if the environmental effect increases or decreases expression of the gene and the biological consequences of that change in expression. In some cases we may only know that an environment is linked to a specific phenotype without knowing the underlying mechanism. This information can still add useful knowledge to the graph. In some cases, the graph itself can be used to infer the pathways leading from the expression of a gene to an observed phenotype.

The semantic representation of the effect of an environmental exposure on gene expression is more straightforward for the effects of a chemical or a substance, like phenol or rubber cement.

Data can be collected in the laboratory using model organisms and the results added to the graph for analysis. Every day environmental exposures are rarely this simple and frequently involve exposure to many types of substances in different contexts, like climate or socioeconomic status.

Despite having the graph available to quickly explore the data and locate genes of interest, the workflow for comparing the promoter regions required substantial manual intervention. In this instance, we only had 16 gene pairs to explore, but scaling up these types of analyses will require the ability to traverse data annotated with gene identifiers and data annotated with gene coordinates.

In the future, someone should investigate conservation vs con-conservation of cis and trans regulatory regions of genes that may help understand inter- and intraspecies response to stress and adaptation

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the National Science Foundation grant awards #1940330, #1939945, #1940059, and #1940062.

The authors would like to thank Sierra Moxon and Harry Caufield for technical assistance and helpful conversation.

CyVerse is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation grant awards #0735191, #1265383, and #1743442.

Supplemental Data

All supplemental data files can be accessed in GitHub under a CC-0 license (https://github.com/diatomsRcool/supplementary_material/tree/main/promoter_region).

- 1) drought_expression.tsv
- 2) drought_genes.tsv
- 3) GO_annotations.tsv
- 4) panther_results folder
- 5) promoter_region_clustvis_data0.tsv
- 6) orthologous_genes.tsv

Clustvis analysis is at <https://biit.cs.ut.ee/clustvis/?s=IWJNurmUtGWZoMt>

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